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A Conceptual Model of the Role of Perception of Celebrity Endorsement in Consumer Purchase Intention of MS Glow Beauty Products

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Abstract

This article aims to explain the influence of perception of celebrity endorser on purchase intention which is mediated by attitude towards ads and attitude towards brand. This study was moderated by the type of endorser tested in two groups, handsome vs. not handsome endorser types. Literature reviews made by several international journals with high reputation including research from Schouten et al. (2020) and Ha & Lam (2017). This article is to identify the variables used to build a conceptual model. The expected finding is that there is a positive relationship between perception of celebrity endorser, attitude towards ads and attitude towards brand on purchase intention which is moderated by type of endorser. This study also explains the dimensions of trustworthiness, expertise, and similarity that produce the perception of celebrity endorsers. Researchers hope this research can help marketers to design effective marketing strategies to influence potential consumers. This paper is also expected to contribute theoretically, practically and possibly can be used for future studies.

Keywords: Perception of Celebrity Endorser, Attitude Towards Ads, Attitude Towards Brand, Purchase Intention

1. Introduction

Social media users are not limited to individuals, rather social media can serve as a platform for organizations, businesses, goals or brands (Kim & Ko, 2012). Social Media can be used to create content and reach others. For businesses or brands, it can often be confusing to understand how they can influence and engage in conversations with their customers. Social media is a low-cost and easy-to-use marketing platform for promoting a brand to consumers. It is important to understand what factors influence consumers to recognize brands on social media and the effects of promotion on social media (McClure & Kyoung, 2020). When social media changes from a communication medium to a product marketing medium, it is important for brands to understand the influence of social media platforms on consumer attitudes and purchase intentions.

The last decade has seen major changes in the effectiveness of social media marketing marked by a shift towards celebrity endorsements (Bergkvist & Zhou, 2016). The growth of celebrity endorsement marketing accelerated

with the emergence of COVID 19, where people are turning from offline to online for entertainment and virtual social experiences. In 2021 semester 1, e-commerce transactions grew by 63.4% to Rp. 186.7 trillion compared to the previous year (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2021). As a result, celebrity endorsement marketing has become an important part of digital marketing strategy as a touchpoint to reach target consumers. The selection of celebrities that are adjusted to the target market and other facilities that can support the buyer's decision-making process is used as a benchmark for companies in choosing promotional tools (Freire et al., 2018). Selection of endorsers, especially for beauty products, often uses celebrities who have good physical attractiveness to market these beauty products. But not all beauty products use beautiful or handsome celebrities for marketing their products.

The selection of celebrity in the advertising marketing of Ms Glow's beauty products is interesting to study. The advertising strategy chosen uses a famous Korean celebrity, namely Cha Eun Woo, who holds the title as a Korean actor with a handsome face, which is an interesting marketing technique (Kompas.com, 2022). On the other hand, Ms Glow also carried out a marketing strategy using a unique celebrity. The selection of celebrities such as Marshel Widianto, who has an unattractive face and appearance and is not a model who often appears for beauty products, tries to break people's perceptions that beauty models must be beautiful or handsome (Gusniar, 2020). Celebrity's background, namely as a comedian, has nothing to do with the products being marketed, namely beauty products. Ms Glow's beauty product wants to show consumers that one's looks and appearance are not the main thing because everyone has the right to take care of themselves. The effectiveness of the endorser depends on the intent he brings to the endorsement process (McCracken, 1989; Hussain et al., 2020).

The MS Glow brand also has advantages in the local market in the world of beauty in the skincare category for various ages from children, adolescents, adults to the elderly. Their products can also be used not only for women but also produce products for men. The high market demand for MS Glow products is evidenced by the high sales figures compared to other local skincare products. MS Glow is the best-selling local skincare top brand with a total sales value of IDR 38.5 billion in the period 1-18 February 2021 (Compas.co.id, 2021). This proves the high number of MS Glow skincare sales in e-commerce. This shows a good market potential to advance the skincare market share in the local product category.

Perception of celebrity endorsers is a representation of consumer confidence that the celebrity has a good image and is suitable for advertising the product of a company brand, in this case the use of celebrity aims to gain greater consumer trust and marketing effectiveness (Goldsmith, et al., 2000; Freire et al., 2018; Schouten, 2020). Consumer perceptions of celebrity endorsements are based on celebrity dimensions that influence purchase intention, namely trustworthiness, expertise, similarity (Gauns et al., 2017). Consumer perceptions of the effectiveness of advertising with celebrity endorsers also aim to shape consumer attitudes that can influence purchase intentions.

Attitude towards ads is the feeling of consumers to judge whether certain advertisements are good or bad (Felix & Borges, 2014). The formation of an attitude towards ads is influenced by the content of the advertisement itself (Sallam & Algammash, 2016; Sarashadi & Amina, 2018). The effectiveness of advertising with celebrity endorsers aims to shape consumer attitudes that can influence purchase intentions. After receiving a stimulus from an advertisement, someone will tend to respond to how that person can behave towards the advertisement and trigger an intention to buy.

Attitude towards brand is the consumer's perception of trust and expertise in the brand (Felix & Borges, 2014; Felbert & Breuer, 2020). Attitude towards brand is a feeling that evaluates positively or negatively, good or bad, likes or dislikes a product (Sauro, 2015). Attitude towards the brand can be interpreted as the consumer's feelings towards the company's way to be trusted and able to fulfill its claims on the brand. The formation of an attitude towards a brand is also influenced by the effectiveness of advertisements using celebrity endorsers (Bergkvist & Zhou, 2016; Schouten et al., 2020).

Purchase intention is a process of consumer behavior towards certain products and consumers' willingness to buy these products based on their overall assessment (Kotler, 2016; Wang et al., 2017). Purchase intention is the desire of consumers to buy which is part of the process towards the purchase action. Celebrity endorsers can generate

better opinions about advertisements and brands which tend to have a positive impact on consumer purchase intentions (Tanjung & Hudrasyah, 2016).

The use of 2 different celebrity appearances is interesting to study to investigate the effectiveness of the advertisements produced in influencing consumer purchase intentions. Referring to previous studies examined by Schouten et al. (2020) there are limitations to the study, namely only identifying the impact of celebrity support vs. influencers on advertising effectiveness (attitudes towards advertisements and products, and purchase intentions), moderated by the suitability of supporting products, so that they have not studied consumer perceptions of celebrity endorsers. In addition, this study investigates two potential mediators that underlie this relationship, namely identification (perceived similarity and identification of expectations) and credibility (trust and expertise). The results obtained show that participants identify more with influencers than celebrities, feel more like influencers than celebrities, and trust influencers more than celebrities. In terms of advertising effectiveness, similarity, identification of expectations, and trust mediate the relationship between the type of endorser and advertising effectiveness. The research conducted by Ha & Lam (2017) examines several factors that influence purchase intentions, namely celebrity endorsements and customer attitudes toward brands conducted on customers in Vietnam. The results showed that customer attitudes toward brands were positively influenced by three factors, namely celebrity compatibility with the brand/product, celebrity trust, and celebrity expertise. Attitude towards the brand also has a positive impact on customer purchase intentions. In a study by Schouten et al. (2020) and Ha & Lam (2017) are expected to be able to add other factors that influence purchase intention in the future with different methods and contexts.

Based on the explanation above, the authors conducted this research to see whether using two celebrities is an effective promotion for product or brand. So the authors conducted research to determine whether there is a positive relationship between perception of celebrity endorsement, attitude towards ads and attitude towards brand on purchase intention which is moderated by the type of endorser. This study also explains the dimensions of trustworthiness, expertise, and similarity that shape the perception of celebrity endorsement.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis

2.1. Core Theory

The conceptual model in this study is based on cognitive psychology theory. According to Schiffman & Wisenblit (2019), cognitive psychology theory explains that consumer behavior consists of three components, namely cognitive, affective and conative. This cognitive component describes the knowledge and perception of an attitude object. Someone has confidence from what is seen or what is known. Furthermore, this affective component describes a person's feelings or emotions towards an object. Affective is a person's overall evaluation of an object whether it is good or bad, likes or dislikes. Then the last, namely the conative component describes a person's tendency to take certain actions related to objects. In this conative a person has an interest and action in a behavior so that consumers have a decision on that object. The application in the formation of the conceptual model is the perception of celebrity endorser which has the dimensions of trustworthiness, expertise, and similarity which is a cognitive psychology component that produces an affective component in the form of attitude towards ads and attitude towards brand and a conative component in the form of purchase intention which is moderated by the type of endorser.

2.2. Purchase Intentions

Purchase intention is a combination of consumer interest in purchasing products (Kim & Ko, 2012; Tanjung & Hudrasyah, 2016; Wang et al., 2017). Intention is an internal factor that influences consumer behavior, interest is a form of thought that is real from the reflection of consumer plans to buy a product (Goldsmith et al., 2000). According to Setiadi (2003), indicators of purchase intention are interest, attitude of paying attention to the product, and the desire to buy based on needs. Purchase intention is a stage carried out by consumers before planning to buy a product (Yeh & In, 2010; Kotler, 2016; Rachbini, 2018). Based on this opinion, buying interest can be interpreted as a desire to buy which is part of the process leading to purchasing actions carried out by a

consumer. A successful endorser will create customer awareness for a product, so that they will form a positive attitude towards the brand and generate an intention to make a purchase (Sarashadi & Amina, 2018).

2.3. Perception of Celebrity Endorser

Perception of celebrity endorsers is the consumer's interpretation of a celebrity endorser through the senses that are influenced by internal and external factors of an endorser in conveying advertising messages (Ohanian, 1990; Solso et al., 2007; Gauns et al., 2017). Perception is a cognitive process experienced by everyone in receiving a stimulus and trying to understand a meaningful situation. Celebrity endorsers can bring consumers positive or negative perceptions of a product (Freire et al., 2018). Celebrity Endorser is defined as someone who conveys a message to consumers who can form opinions and then consumers will forward these opinions according to their respective perceptions. When a celebrity endorser advertises a product, the celebrity endorser's self-image will affect a company, brand or product. There are several dimensions of celebrity endorsers that can attract attention and can influence consumer perceptions to make purchasing decisions (Gauns et al., 2017). Several dimensions affect the perception of a celebrity endorser, namely trustworthiness, expertise, and similarity.

2.4. Trustworthiness, Expertise, Similarity

Trustworthiness refers to the honesty, integrity and trust of an endorser (Endorgen, 1999; Freire et al., 2018; Gusniar, 2020). Consumer preference for endorsers generally has the impression that the endorser is a reliable source of information. Whereas expertise is a process of how far a celebrity endorser is considered qualified enough to provide valid and accurate information in discussing certain subjects based on experience, quality, knowledge, expertise and skills (Rameez & Ahmed, 2014). The expertise possessed by the endorser must be able to have a positive and pleasant effect on consumers, so as to be able to influence the recipient of the information to consider purchasing. Meanwhile, the similarity dimension itself refers to similarities between celebrity endorsers and intended consumers (McCracken, 1989; Munnukka et al., 2016; Schouten et al., 2020). These similarities include similarities in nature, hobbies, needs, etc.

When a product is advertised by a celebrity who can be trusted, and has expertise and similarities with consumers, the effectiveness of advertising will be higher in influencing consumer attitudes (Kotler, 2016). Celebrities that consumers can trust tend to form positive attitudes toward advertisements and brands. Previous studies have explained that consumer perceptions of a good celebrity endorser have a positive effect on influencing attitudes toward advertising (Goldsmith et al., 2000). On the other hand, when consumers have a positive perception of the advertised celebrity endorser, a positive attitude towards the brand will be formed (Ohanian, 1990; Ha & Lam, 2017). Based on these guidelines, the hypothesis is conceptualized as follows:

H1: Perception of celebrity endorser has a positive effect on attitude towards ads

H2: Perception of celebrity endorser has a positive effect on attitude towards brand

2.5. Attitude Towards Ads

Attitude towards ads is a person's likes or dislikes for certain advertising objects (Arnould et al., 2005; Munnukka et al., 2016; Haryanto & Nusantara, 2018). After receiving a stimulus from an advertisement, someone will tend to respond to how that person can behave towards the advertisement. It can be said that attitude towards ads is a person's feelings of interest in an advertisement. When viewing an advertisement, consumers have a response or perception of the advertisement, thereby forming purchase intentions for the product (Jhally, 2003; Thomas & Johnson, 2017; Fam & Waller, 2006). Research by Haryanto & Nusantara (2018) also confirms that in the process of consumer behavior to buy, consumer buying interest is influenced by attitudes towards brands and attitudes towards advertisements. It can be concluded that the higher the positive attitude towards the advertisement, the higher the intention to buy the product. Based on these guidelines, the hypothesis is conceptualized as follows:

H3: Attitude towards ads has a positive effect on purchase intention

2.6. Attitude Towards Brands

Attitude towards the brand is a consumer evaluation of a brand as a whole after watching advertisements on brands that have a beneficial or detrimental impact on a brand (Sallam & Algammash, 2016; Ha & Lam, 2017). This understanding implies that the attitude towards the brand is a process of consumer learning towards the brand to evaluate the brand so that it will form a choice whether the brand is considered good or not good. Fournier (1998) and Wang et al. (2017) said that if a brand fulfills consumer desires, it will have an impact on psychological effects where consumers will tend to be loyal to a brand and will increase the desire to purchase the product. Many studies explain that in the process of behavior there is a significant and positive relationship between positive attitudes and purchase intentions towards brands. This shows that a higher positive attitude towards a brand means a higher purchase intention (Haryanto, 2014; McCormick, 2016; Ha & Lam, 2017). This means that the higher the positive attitude towards the brand, the higher the intention to buy the brand. Based on these guidelines, the hypothesis is conceptualized as follows:

H4: Attitude towards brand has a positive effect on purchase intention

2.7. Type of Endorser

Endorsers are advertisement supporters or also known as advertisement stars who support advertised products (Biswas et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2017; Sarashadi & Amina, 2018). Many factors are considered by producers in choosing the type of endorser according to the needs of advertising effectiveness. Various types of endorsers have their own charm to influence consumers and influence consumer buying behavior so that they can make purchasing decisions for advertised products. Ads delivered by endorsers must be able to form opinions that are in accordance with what the company wants (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

According to research by Yeh & In (2010) in an advertisement there is an influence of different types of endorsers on attitudes towards advertisements, attitudes towards brands and consumer purchase intentions. Although in another study conducted by Schouten et al. (2020) revealed that there was no direct effect of the type of endorser on advertising and product attitudes, but there were several mediating effects through trust, similarity and identification which could explain the relationship between the type of endorser and advertising effectiveness. Many previous studies have explained that there is a different effect on each type of endorser depending on the case (Tanjung & Hudrasyah, 2016; Zhu et al., 2019; von Felbert & Breuer, 2020). But there is no research that explains the type of endorser according to handsome vs not handsome appearance. So it is useful in this study to determine whether the type of endorser according to the appearance of handsome vs not handsome can moderate the relationship between perceptions of celebrity endorsers, attitudes towards advertising, attitudes towards brands and consumer purchase intentions. So that the hypothesis is conceptualized as follows:

H5: Type of endorser moderate the relationship between perception of celebrity endorser and attitude towards ads

H6: Type of endorser moderate the relationship between perception of celebrity endorser and attitude towards brand

H7: Type of endorser moderate the relationship between attitude towards ads and purchase intention

H8: Type of endorser moderate the relationship between attitude towards brand and purchase intention

Based on the development of the conceptualized hypothesis, FIGURE 1 below is the resulting conceptual model framework.

Figure 1 : A conceptual model that explains the relationship between perception of celebrity endorser and purchase intention mediated by attitude towards ads and attitude towards brand and moderated by type of endorser

Figure 1 explains that the dimensions behind the perception of a celebrity endorser include trustworthiness, expertise, and similarity to the endorser. When the information stimulus conveyed by the endorser has coherence with the values that exist within the individual, the perception will be easier to accept (Toha, 2003). When consumers begin to form positive perceptions of celebrity endorsers, it is hoped that this situation can form positive attitudes towards advertising and positive attitudes towards brands moderated by the type of endorser. Thus, attitudes towards advertising and attitudes towards brands play an important role in influencing purchase intentions which are moderated by the type of endorser (Felix & Borges, 2014).

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Design

This research uses a quantitative descriptive approach using an online survey method to reach more respondents because this research uses the consumer population in Indonesia. The survey method is a research method used in certain populations and samples and in collecting data using primary data using research instruments that are carried out in a systematic and structured manner with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). The data collection for this study used cross-sectional, because this research was only conducted at one time and described the situation at one time only.

3.2. Source of Data

The data sources used in this research are primary and secondary data. Primary data is data that is directly collected and analyzed by researchers themselves (Sekaran et al., 2016). The primary data in this study is the result of the direct responses of the respondents in answering the questions on each questionnaire instrument via Google Form. Secondary data in this study were obtained from literature reviews, journals, websites and previous research to find data or quotes from several definitions which were used as references as a theoretical basis.

3.3. Population, Sample and Sampling Technique

3.3.1. Population

The population that will be studied in this study are consumers in Indonesia who intend to purchase MS Glow products by viewing advertisements by Cha Eun Woo and Marshel Widiyanto. The population of this study uses consumers with an age range of 17-60 years. This population was taken in accordance with the age provisions for

using MS Glow products, namely from 17 years old to the elderly. According to Sekaran et al. (2016) population is a group of people as a whole, as well as all events, things or interests in it that the researcher wants to investigate.

3.3.2. Sample

The sample in this study were consumers in Indonesia who saw advertisements by Cha Eun Woo and Marshel Widiyanto who specifically had the intention to buy MS Glow products who were in the age range of 17-60 years. The number of samples that will be used in this study is as many as 300 respondents with the aim that the results obtained have the desired level of accuracy. According to Hair et al. (2017) determining the minimum sample size for SEM is $(\text{Number of indicators} + \text{number of latent variables}) \times (5 \text{ to } 10 \text{ times})$. This sample was divided according to the endorser type testing group, namely 150 respondents to Cha Eun Woo's ad and 150 respondents to Marshel Widiyanto's ad.

3.3.3. Sampling Technique

The sampling technique for this study used a purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling is a technique for determining samples based on populations that have certain considerations or characteristics (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). Individuals who see advertisements by Cha Eun Woo and Marshel Widiyanto and have the intention to buy MS Glow products are the criteria for sampling size.

3.4. Data collection technique

Data collection was carried out using the questionnaire method, namely written questions that had been formulated beforehand. Data collection is shared online, via Whatsapp message, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter so that it reaches the intended target. The measurement scale used is the Likeart scale to find out how strong the respondents are in agreeing with the statements given (Sekaran et al., 2016). Respondents' answers were categorized using 5 points, namely:

- a. Point 5 means Strongly Agree (SS)
- b. Point 4 means Agree (S)
- c. Point 3 means Neutral (N)
- d. Point 2 means Disagree (TS)
- e. Point 1 means Strongly Disagree (STS)

3.5. Data analysis

This study used a Structural Equation Model (SEM) with the Partial Least Square (PLS) program using SmartPLS 3 software. In this study, Multi Group SEM analysis was used because there were two groups of sample data in the study. The data sample groups used were the Cha Eun Woo ad group and the Marshel Widiyanto ad group. There are two sub-models in using SEM analysis, namely the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model). The measurement model explains how manifest variables represent latent variables. Evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) is carried out to assess the validity and reliability of the model. Meanwhile, the structural model (inner model) explains the strength between construct variables.

3.6. Outer Model

3.6.1. Validity test

Measuring whether or not the questionnaire is accepted can use a validity test. Validity assessment includes convergent validity and discriminant validity. The criteria for evaluating convergent validity and discriminatory validity are as follows:

- a. Convergent Validity. Convergent validity is said to be fulfilled if two different instruments used to measure the same concept have highly correlated values (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Convergent validity test was carried out using the AVE (Average variance Extracted) value and outer loading. The expected value of outer

loading > 0.7 is declared valid. Meanwhile, the AVE value is considered to explain more than half of the indicator variance if it has a value of 0.50 or higher.

- b. Discriminant Validity. This value is the value of the cross loading factor which is useful for knowing whether the construct has adequate discriminant, namely by comparing the value of the outer loading on the intended construct it must be greater than the value of the cross loading with other constructs. If the cross loading value exceeds the outer loading value, this indicates that there is a problem with discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2017).

3.6.2. Reliability Test

Reliability testing is carried out to prove the accuracy, consistency, and precision of the instrument in measuring constructs. Testing the reliability of a construct with reflective indicators can be done by assessing Cronbach's Alpha and AVE (Average Variance Extracted). Consistent respondent answers characterize a reliable questionnaire. The results can be said to be reliable if the Cronbach alpha value is > 0.7 and the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) score is > 0.5 (Hair et al., 2017).

3.7. Inner Model

The assessment of the structural model (inner model) uses SEM by looking at the R-Square value for each endogenous latent variable as the predictive power of the structural model. The R-Square value is a goodness fit model test. Changes in the R-Square value are used to explain the effect of certain exogenous latent variables on endogenous variables, whether they have a substantive effect. The results of the R-Square represent the total variance of the constructs described by the model. The results are said to be strong if the R-Square is > 0.67 (Hair et al., 2017).

The Goodness of Fit (GOF) value is used to evaluate the inner model. The goodness of fit (GoF) index is an operational solution to problems because it can be interpreted as an index to validate models globally (Hair et al., 2017). Testing this test can be calculated using:

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE \times R^2}$$

From these results it will show whether the model is fit or not by looking at the value, namely 0.10 = small, 0.25 = medium, 0.38 = large (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

3.8. Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing can be done with the bootstrapping method. Hypothesis testing by looking at the probability value (p value) or t value in each hypothesis. The results can be seen in the statistical t value, if the results show t > 1.96, it can be concluded that there is a significant effect between variables. Another alternative can be seen if the p value score < 0.05, it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between variables (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

3.9. Moderation Test

In this study, to test both groups of types of endorsers, the analysis model was carried out using the Multi Group Analysis Structural Equation Model. The Multi-Group Analysis stage was carried out to find out whether there is a significant difference in effect between the two types of endorsers. The test results can be seen from the results of the path coefficient difference scores and their significance (p value). If the p-value ≤ 0.05 then the difference in the parameters analyzed between groups is significant. And the p-value ≥ 0.05, the difference in the parameters analyzed between groups is not significant (Hair et al., 2017).

4. Conclusion

This conceptual model provides an alternative model that is different from previous research on the impact of celebrity vs. endorsement influencers on advertising effectiveness, so they have not studied advertising effectiveness based on consumer perceptions of celebrity endorsers moderated by type of endorser based on handsome vs not handsome (Schouten et al., 2020). In addition, consumers consider the effectiveness of advertising using celebrity endorsers to produce positive consumer attitudes towards advertisements and brands so that they can trigger purchase intentions (Ha & Lam, 2017). The dimensions of trustworthiness, expertise, similarity which affect the perception of celebrity endorsers play an important role in purchasing decisions (Gauns et al., 2017). This model is a role model that can be used as a reference and applied to marketers to design effective advertising marketing strategies to influence potential consumers. Practically, this research provides an understanding for marketers about the role of perception of celebrity endorser on purchase intention by taking into account variables such as attitude towards ads and attitude towards brand.

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